

ReBioCycle

Project Factsheet

A new European blueprint for circular bioplastics upcycling solutions

The Challenge

The integration of biobased biodegradable plastics into the circular economy requires the establishment of collection and sorting strategies for biobased biodegradable plastics that are compatible with current waste management practices and their subsequent recycling through novel technologies. The recycling of biobased plastics into recycled high-performing materials is a key challenge. Biobased plastic waste does not yet constitute a relevant amount of the total plastic waste (being only 1% in weight). Still, due to their high weight in the political agenda, it is easy to foresee that biobased plastics will gain a relevant market share in the near future.

Project Snapshot

Type of project: Innovation Action

Funded by: Circular Bio-based Europe (CBE), European Union, Horizon Europe Programme

Duration: 1 October 2024– 30 September 2028

Total costs: € 10 416 832

CBE funding: € 7 497 0001

Project Coordinator: University College Dublin, BiOrbic

Contact: Prof. Kevin O'Connor

Our Approach

ReBioCycle proves a portfolio of bioplastic sorting and recycling technologies within three complementary waste-processor-centric hubs at a demonstration scale and in the real operational environment the effective and efficient recycling of three types of bioplastics (PLA, PHA, and composites) to demonstrate a higher impact of obtaining the same or superior grade recycled polymers and other higher value applications.

ReBioCycle Impacts

Improve circularity and resource efficiency via practical application of the circular bioeconomy concept in the biobased and biodegradable plastics value chain.

Scale up effective sorting and recycling schemes for biobased and biodegradable plastic materials.

Increase the recycled content in new products from biobased and biodegradable plastics.

Improve the environmental performance across the value chain against fossil or biobased benchmarks.

Achieve better social acceptance of circular biobased solutions and products.

ReBioCycle has received funding from the Circular Bio-based Joint Undertaking (JU) and its members under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101156032. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

The Hubs: Work Plan

The Dutch Hub: Upscaling chemical technology to TRL6 to recycle PLA and PHA with TORWASH technology.

The Spanish Hub: Upscaling enzymatic and mechanical recycling technologies to TRL6 and TRL7 respectively, to achieve rPLA and rPHA.

The Italian Hub: Upscaling chemical technology to TRL 7 to achieve rComposites.

ReBioCycle will:

- Develop sorting and separation systems for isolating dedicated bio-based plastics from the mixed biobased and fossil-based plastics streams.
- Develop, upscale and deploy innovative recycling technologies and adapt, optimise and deploy existing ones for biobased plastics. The focus is on mechanical, chemical, microbial and enzymatic technologies.
- Demonstrate integration of the recycling process(es) at a relevant scale inside a real waste management plant.
- Target as much as possible the same grade for the recycled as the virgin product (e.g. keeping food grade) and upgrade the resulting stream into higher-value products.
- Assess the market uptake potential of recycled biobased plastic products.
- Assess the integration of the developed sorting and recycling technologies with current waste management practices.
- Involve waste management companies.
- Perform an assessment based on the safe and sustainable by design (SSbD) framework, developed by the European Commission, for assessing the safety and sustainability of chemicals and materials.
- Develop recommendations that can advance further the application of the SSbD framework.

Project Partners

ReBioCycle implements a multi-actor approach and involves key actors and stakeholders, such as waste management companies, packaging producers and brand owners. The consortium consists of universities, waste management sites; bioplastic recycling technology partners; SMEs; product validation partners, communication and exploitation partners, life cycle assessment and SSbD partners, bioplastics brand owners, thus a well-balanced combination of relevant knowledge supported by research and gaming cluster experts with proven track-records and targeted roles.

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